

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE DIGITALISATION OF EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract: The article "The Role of Women in the Digitalisation of Education: Challenges and Opportunities" studies the vital role of women in education in the digital age. It stresses the importance of women having a thorough knowledge of technology to overcome the lost chances and improve educational results. The paper stresses how technology can be used to connect people from different places, give women a chance to be independent and create the learning experience that suits the person. Moreover, it also deals with past, and current problems like the digital gender gap and the future opportunities in digital education for women in rural areas. The article shows the role of women in digital education can be seen in the changing world of ed-tech and the necessity of the promotion of gender equality in education access and outcomes.

Keywords: digitalization, education, technology, learning, gender.

РОЛЬ ЖЕНЩИН В ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ

Аннотация: В статье «Роль женщин в цифровизации образования: вызовы и возможности» исследуется жизненно важная роль женщин в образовании в эпоху цифровых технологий. В нем подчеркивается важность наличия у женщин глубоких знаний технологий для преодоления упущенных шансов и улучшения результатов образования. В документе подчеркивается, как технологии могут использоваться для объединения людей из разных мест, предоставления женщинам возможности быть независимыми и создания опыта обучения, который подходит человеку. Помимо этого, в нем также рассматриваются прошлые и текущие проблемы, такие как цифровой гендерный разрыв и будущие возможности цифрового образования для женщин в сельской местности. Статья автора всеобъемлющей статьи показывает, что роль женщин в цифровом образовании можно увидеть в меняющемся мире образовательных технологий и необходимости продвижения гендерного равенства в доступе к образованию и его результатах.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, образование, технологии, обучение, гендер.

Importance of Women in Education

Women and adolescent girls must also benefit from the unexpurgated digit sustainability transfigurement represented by digitalisation induced by OECD judicial arrangements (Xu et al., 2022). Women must have fulsome digital literacy, as this may counteract any denied opportunities. Technologies have the potential to enhance the education of millennial women and people among them, and the straightforward implementation of technology can accelerate these methods. Subsequently, we must still contemplate interventions that support the woman's director through administration, enacting mechanization, and preparation.

Many women can be excluded in arid areas of the world including the Far East and the Middle East. However, digital education accelerates this process and can break these geographic barriers, chagrin and people with disabilities. Many studies (M S & Siddiqui, 2023) show that digital technologies are utilized by several users to personalize learning processes, which is critical for women who must manage the work-life balance constantly. Language faculty are addressing limitations on opportunities to learn for several women in many multilingual and formal learning settings. Technology also allows users to use social media as emboldening and enlightenment to enhance access to modules and training resources relevant to their courses. Instructors who were focused on advancing women's erudition were central to enhancing access to resources as they listened to their ideas and requirements, and fostered their autonomy; and curricula developers and knowing directors used this information to improve access to assets for their learners. Technological growth often has many female-led aspirants who render the efficacy of investments on honesty and resource allocation and impact analysis. According to the EHRC's research, role models and positive influences on students' digital skills were considered as women teachers and women role models. In the report "The digital gender gap in teacher education: the TPACK framework for the 21st century", for instance, it is stated that women are still less represented in the field of technology design and programming, thus being at the heart of the digital divide which mostly affects primary and secondary education students (María Gómez-Trigueros & Yáñez de Aldecoa, 2021).

Historical Contributions

Education is crucial for social advancement, economic stability, and gender equality, yet disparities remain in educational achievements for women and men. Reviews reveal that girls tend to differ from boys in a wide range of factory settings, in part explaining differences in academic performance and choices of educational fields. Gender disparities in educational attainment have long-term consequences, influencing, inter alia, income, power, health, and mate selection. Parental education is a significant factor shaping children's educational opportunities and their attitudes towards learning (Belingheri et al., 2021). The focus of the aforementioned research unfolds in developed countries, yet it is equally relevant for developing countries. Reduced access to and completion of school tied to utility theory and human capital theory, both of which are based on households striving to maximize utility and parents recognizing that educating their sons contributes to household income and sustaining the family. Parents therefore face a trade-off giving priority to having sons go to school, consistent with boys surpassing girls in educational investment and attainment, including effectiveness in learning and retention. Approaches centring on school-level factors contributing to disparities in educational opportunities have been gaining considerable traction in recent years. These include classroom environments, instructional strategies, curriculum content and resources, learning outcomes, and school resources.

Observing gender differences in technology use, prior studies have found no gender disparities in using online education in offline learning environments. Learners may show the least striking preferences for a given teaching medium despite gender even out of a crisis. Females tend to hold significantly fewer positive opinions about technology in the study conducted in China (Zhou & Mou, 2022). The less favourable attitudes toward technology held by females than males were first observed in online education across genders. Prior research on telephone interviews suggests some significant gender differences, such as males tend to have more

favourable attitudes towards technology than females, perform tasks more quickly, and prefer information exchange than females. It is also worth noting that there were no gender differences that were examined on the belief about technology, affect, and self-efficacy in the study. The belief about technology refers to a general cognitive view about the nature of technology. Affect refers to the feelings, emotions, or moods that participants associate with the use of technology, whereas self-efficacy is more about people's capability of how well they can perform certain tasks with the technology.

Current Challenges

Currently, the digital divide, usually described as the gap in individuals' access to ICTs, is one of the major challenges in digitalising education. The gender digital gap especially is a significant problem in education. The digital gender gap stems primarily from two issues—differences in access to technology and differences in available time to use it, combined with the prejudices that affect the employment and claim to technology by many women. Researchers show that women have worse digital access due to cultural, legal, and financial constraints. They often have more limited Internet access, lower rates of digital literacy, and less access to devices such as computers and smartphones than men. Additionally, women use the Internet less frequently than men for multiple reasons, including time, money, and autonomy. Such gendered differences in the digital divide were barely noticeable before the pandemic but have grown during the crisis. One of the primary reasons is that the combined fallout from the digital gender gap and the crisis disproportionately burden women compared to men.

Digitalisation revolutionises almost every aspect of life, including education. Since early 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has pushed the digital transformation of education faster than any of the prior initiatives. Even in the past, many education systems had been to some extent digitalised or increasingly integrating digital elements into traditional face-to-face instruction. For instance, educational policies across countries promoted increased use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), smart boards, learning management systems, and massive open online courses, and some of their initiatives were successful, but digitalisation did not reach its full potential until the lockdowns. The Indian educational system is no exception. While the 'Digital India' programme was introduced in 2015 with the vision to transform India into a digital society and provide digital infrastructure to every citizen, the 'digital divide' in India remains large. A significant share of the Indian population is digitally impoverished as there is a significant gender dimension that persists with the use of technology and accessing education.

Future Opportunities

Digital education has given scored on various opportunities for females – especially in rural areas – since females are now confident about their learning through their digital devices as compared to sources of education during a pandemic. A preference for 43% education in the offline channel, while 57% respondents are likely to opt for online learning post-pandemic. Opportunities for females in digital education will be thriving after their encouragement towards digital and lifelong learning. Many conceptions like females are hesitant learners and knowledge receivers can be destructed. Furthermore, females learn passionately when they have control over what and how they learn. Working professionals are being adequately connected to existing resources and new opportunities for growth and discounts. This plays an important role in the changes they make in their learning practices and preferences during and

after the pandemic to ensure digital and lifelong learning. Like digital education has also allowed females to get education especially in decentralized settlements but due to lack of IT services, like no internet reception, or load shedding etc., access to such classes decreases the continuity of their education. Availability of smart gadgets with smart features till the depth of the ever-growing market. Even female learners from rural regions of India now have unlimited access to Android gadgets along with Wi-Fi especially in metro cities. Rural regions of India have been through a severe economic crisis during COVID-19. The women folk are trying to overcome the obstacles by harnessing their inherent skills. Therefore, we believe that the role of women in the digitalisation of education has been outstanding and even going to change drastically.

Digital education trends evolved due to the COVID-19 pandemic growth (M S & Siddiqui, 2023). Education technology literacy is gaining acceptance as the immediate requirement for efficiency in digital pedagogical skills among teachers. With the launch of various programs such as the Digital India campaign, Pratinidhi, Kanya Sumangala, Karmika Kanyadhan, and Kanyakalavay, the field of education has improved significantly due to the promotion of female education by the government (Xu et al., 2022). The trend of Indian digital education grew rapidly due to the availability of affordable smartphones by the government and private companies which has boosted female admissions to educational institutions (Aminul Islam, 2022). Women's education and employment status can boost economic growth due to further increased digitization.

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